

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

IDENTIFICATION OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN *Cyperus rotundus* BY GC-MS ANALYSIS AND THEIR INHIBITORY EFFECT ON DIABETIC COMPLICATIONS THROUGH MOLECULAR DOCKING

Jayashree .S¹, K.Vijayalakshmi², Reena Rosy Thomas³

¹School of Biochemistry, REVA University, Bangalore.

²Department of Biochemistry, Bharathi Women's College, Chennai.

³Division of Social Sciences, IIHR, Bangalore.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 25/06/2018

Available online

02/10/2018

Keywords

Phytochemicals,
C.rotundus, diabetic
retinopathy,

ABSTRACT

The presence of biologically active phytochemicals in medicinal plants contribute to their health benefits. A wide plant derived phytochemicals demonstrated bioactivity against diabetes and its complications. Our study concentrates on these bioactive compounds derived from *Cyperus rotundus* analysed through GCMS and docking them with the enzyme of polyol pathway Aldose Reductase (AR) responsible for diabetic retinopathy and other diabetic complications. AR inhibition studies have found that phytochemicals derived from plants be a good inhibitors of AR. The dichloro acetic acid (DCA) and Linoleic acid (9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z) are identified bioactive compound showed a significant binding which indicates *Cyperus rotundus* may act as an inhibitor of enzyme and diabetic retinopathy.

Corresponding author

Dr .Jayashree .S

School of Biochemistry, REVA University, Bangalore.

jayashrees@reva.edu.in

Please cite this article in press as **Jayashree .S** et al. Identification of Bioactive compounds in *Cyperus rotundus* by GC-MS Analysis and their inhibitory effect on Diabetic complications through Molecular Docking. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(09).

INTRODUCTION

Indian systems of medicines shows that the natural herbal products is much effective in the treatment of numerous diseases. For many centuries plants have provided a rich source of therapeutic agents and bases for synthetic drugs.¹⁸ *Cyperus rotundus* (Nagarmotha) a member of Cyperaceae has gained its own recognition in the principles of Ayurveda. It grows in tropical sub-tropical and temperate regions. It has many pharmaceutical characteristics such as to cure diabetes, control diarrhoea, prevent the formation of free radicals, holding anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic properties and thus has proved to be a multi-purpose medicinal herb²⁴ The aim of our present study is to identify the bioactive compounds of *C. rotundus* by performing GC-MS analysis and their inhibitory activity on Aldose reductase a key enzyme of polyol pathway which involves in diabetic retinopathy by *in silico* method. (docking.)

Methodology:

Cyperus rotundus tubers without any defect were procured from local market in Bangalore. The samples are authenticated by Dr. Jawahar, Botanist, Institute of Ayurveda & Integrative medicine (FRLHT) Bangalore. The document is preserved. External skins of tubers were removed and the tubers with uniform size were selected for the experiments.

Preparation of the extract

50g of *Cyperus rotundus* in the form of tubers were homogenized in 100ml of methanol using a blender at high speed for one minute at 4°C. The extract was stirred 10 minutes at 4°C and filtered through four layers of cheese cloth and the residue was re-extracted under the same condition with 100ml of methanol. The combined filtrate was concentrated under vacuum at 65°C to dryness and the dry residue was dissolved in methanol. The methanolic extract was used for the analysis²³.

GC-MS Analysis

After the preliminary phytochemical screening, the extract was subjected to GC-MS Analysis to identify the bioactive compounds present in the extract. The analysis of the extract was done by GC/MS Clarus 500 (Perkin Elmer) comprising Restek RtxR column with the dimensions of 30 meter X 0.25 mm using 5% diphenyl /95% dimethyl poly siloxane and the oven temperature and injector temperature is maintained as 40°C and 280°C respectively with the injection volume of 1.0µl for 60 minutes as running time. Interpretation on mass spectrum of GC-MS was done using the database of National Institute Standard and Technology (NIST) having more than 62,000 patterns. The mass spectrum of the unknown component was compared with the spectrum of the standard components stored in the NIST library¹⁹.

ADMET Analysis

ADMET is one of the protocol which is hand for the pharmacokinetics studies and it includes the parameters such as Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion and Toxicity which were finalized by this protocol in two means such as probability and levels of molecular activity. ADMET descriptors analysis module of Accelrys Discovery Studio 2.0 was taken to study the ADMET properties of the selected chemical compounds. The following properties are to be satisfied by the compounds to proceed with docking and they are brain blood barrier (BBB) absorption, solubility, hepatotoxicity, and cytochrome binding P450 oxidase and plasma protein binding (PPB)²¹. The compounds that passed the ADMET were then used for molecular docking studies. Molecular docking is the "best fit" positioning of a ligand that connects to a protein of relevance (E. R. Laird and W. L. Jorgensen, 1990). Achievement of an optimized conformation of protein and ligand and orientation between protein and ligand with the minimization of free energy of overall system is the ultimate aim of docking. Docking programs such as CDOCKER, LibDock, and Ligand Fit. Ligand Fit is for this recent research work as it is dependent on a primary orientation coupled to the binding site and it is easier to study their interaction.

RESULTS

GC-MS Analysis

In GC-MS Analysis all the main components were separated completely and nine of them are identified using the database of National Institute Standard and Technology (NIST) where their mass spectrum was compared with the spectrum of the known components and are listed in the table 1 with their retention time of major peak and the peak area.

Figure: 01

Figure describes the Chromatogram obtained from the extract by GC-MS analysis.

Table 01.

Sl. No	Sample	Retention time of major peaks	Fragments profile	Compounds matched
1.	CFTRI- 1	28.34	152, 169	DICHLOROACETIC ACID, UNDEC-2-ENYL ESTER, 9,12-OCTADECADIENOIC ACID (Z,Z)
		26.27	171,199, 213,256	TETRADECANOIC ACID, OCTADECANOIC ACID, L-(+)-ASCORBIC ACID 2,6-DIHEXADECANOATE
		28.28	135, 136, 150	2-CHLOROETHYL LINOLEATE, 9,12-OCTADECADIENOIC ACID (Z,Z), ETHYL 9,12-HEXADECADIENOATE

Figure:02.

Figure:03.

C-1 LIQUID SAMPLE

Hit	REV	for	Compound Name
1	872	721	N-HEXADECANOIC ACID
2	844	679	L-(+)-ASCORBIC ACID 2,6-DIHEXADECANOATE
3	835	659	OCTADECANOIC ACID
4	825	672	TETRADECANOIC ACID
5	823	680	N-HEXADECANOIC ACID
6	818	649	TRIDECANOIC ACID
7	817	673	PENTADECANOIC ACID
8	814	662	TRIDECANOIC ACID
9	813	644	TETRADECANOIC ACID
10	812	662	DODECANOIC ACID
11	810	653	DODECANOIC ACID
12	809	659	TRIDECANOIC ACID
13	809	630	OCTADECANOIC ACID
14	808	638	EICOSANOIC ACID
15	806	642	TETRACOSANOIC ACID
16	802	647	DODECANOIC ACID
17	802	643	PENTADECANOIC ACID
18	802	689	N-HEXADECANOIC ACID
19	800	644	EICOSANOIC ACID
20	798	657	UNDECANOIC ACID

C-1 LIQUID SAMPLE

, 18-Feb-2014 + 10:46:27

Sample 2014-120 3237 (26.271) Cm (3231:3243-3192:3215)

3.02e6

Figure:04.

ADMET Analysis:

ADMET, Docking studies & binding energy calculations of compounds with aldose reductase will help to predict their inhibitory effect of the enzyme and thereby on Diabetic retinopathy. The table 02 indicates that the compounds identified in the extract were preferred for docking since the parameters concerned with analysis for the compounds show positive values. Docking of two compounds namely Ethyl 9, 12-hexadecadienoate and Undec-2-enyl ester with aldose reductase were shown in the figures.²⁰

Prediction of the structure of interacted protein ligand complex is the concept of docking (Abraham Donald, 1998). Formation of a stable complex by binding of preferred orientation of one molecule to the second is the method of docking in molecular modeling. Scoring functions such as the strength of the association or binding affinity between two molecules can be predicted from the knowledge of preferred orientation. The relative interaction could affect the signal produced.

Figure: 05

Table :02.

Compounds	Solubilty -Level	BBB_Level	Absorption_Level	Hepatotoxic	CYP2D6	PPB
UNDEC-2-ENYL ESTER	2	0	1	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
9,12-OCTADECADIENOIC ACID (Z,Z)	2	0	1	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
TETRADECANOIC ACID	2	0	0	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
OCTADECANOIC ACID	2	4	3	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
2-CHLOROETHYL LINOLEATE	2	4	3	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
ETHYL 9,12-HEXADECADIENOATE	2	0	1	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE

Binding mode in Molecular Docking

The docking score shows both the compounds are capable of binding to Aldose Reductase. Some of the binding site of Dichloroacetic acid and Linoleic acid with aldose reductase are shown. The binding of the inhibitor with H bonds is also established.

In Undec-2-enyl ester binding hydrogen bonding were observed between carbonyl group and His A; 110, TYR A: 48, CYS A: 298 with respective distance of 2.45, 2.10 and 5.68 Å. In addition, hydrophobic interactions was linking the methyl group of the compound with amino acids of LEU A: 300, TRP A: 111 and TRP A: 219 with respective distance of 4.97, 5.07 and 4.88. Å. The Lib Dock Score is 113.307.

Binding mode of Ethyl 9, 12 – Hexadecadienoate with aldose reductase docking results proved that it interacted with aldose reductase at its ligand binding site with the highest dock score of about 114.503. (Lib Dock Score.) It has interacted by strong hydrogen bond and the bonding was detected among carbonyl group and TRP A: 111 with a distance of 3.02 Å. Also hydrophobic forces was established between the methyl group of the compound with amino acids of His A; 110, TYR A: 48; VAL A: 47 and TRP A: 79 with respective distance of 4.37, 5.44, 3.82 and 4.37 Å.

The complexes found were used for molecular dynamics studies and the result presented that compound c binding with the enzyme is well established which are depicted in the figure 6 and table 2.. The docking analysis signaled that compounds could accommodate with aldose reductase which infers to be a potent aldose reductase inhibitor.

Docking Of Dichloroacetic Acid with Aldose Reductase

Docking Of Linoleic Acid with Aldose Reductase

Binding Of Dichloroacetic Acid through H Bonds

Binding Of Linoleic Acid through H Bonds

Figure 6.

DISCUSSION

Out of nine GC MS analysed compounds of *Cyperus rotundus* six were subjected to ADMET analysis which are mentioned in the table 2. Among them Dichloroacetic acid and Undec-2-enyl ester (Linoleic acid) showed significant binding energy with aldose reductase.

Previous research show the following characteristic features of the identified compound. Also 9,12-Octadecdienoic acid(Z,Z) and Tetra decanoic acid show marked properties. Tetra decanoic acid along with Dichloroacetic acid increases oxidation of glucose by suppressing oxidation of acetate, 3-hydroxybutyrate and palmitate which were observed in diaphragms of alloxan induced diabetic rats and thus decreases the level of glucose by increasing glycolysis. The Tetradecanoic acid prevents the production of free radicals and act as a Lubricant, hypocholesterolemic, and prevents cancer. The 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid(Z,Z) can prevent cardiac diseases and help in curing hair fall in humans¹¹. Ponnamma.*et al.* studies carried on Hexadecanoic acid and Octadecanoic acid on the extract of *Justicia wynaadensis* showed that they also act as antioxidants⁹. The studies on *P. marsupium* showed Tetradecanoic acid (3.47%) and 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (2.49 %) showed their involvement in the inhibition of Aldose reductase activity¹¹. Ethyl ester of 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z) in *Lentinus squarrosulus* ethanolic extracts had significant pharmaceutical activity such as membrane protector, reduction of joint pain, swelling and morning stiffness associated with rheumatoid arthritis.¹³

CONCLUSION

Thus *Cyperus rotundus* contains the bioactive compounds which are having various biological activity concerned with preventing ability of diabetic complications. These compounds act as antioxidant by decreasing free radicals generation, oxidises various metabolites which causes different disorders and proceed as inhibitor of key proteins/enzymes. Thus our study shows the presence of phytochemicals in the *Cyperus rotundus* tubers with pharmaceutical properties as hypocholesteremic, anti inflammation, anti diabetic and inhibit diabetic complications mainly diabetic retinopathy.

REFERENCES

1. Sagrario Martin Aragon, Belen Basabe, Juana M. Benedi and Angel M. Villar. (1998). Antioxidant activity of *Vacciniummyrtillus*L. *Phytother. Res.*, 12: S104 – S106.
2. Hemant R. Jadhav and K.K Bhutani. (2002). Antioxidant properties of Indian Medicinal plants. *Phytother. Res.*, 16: 771 – 773.
3. Slater TF (1984) 'Free radical mechanisms in tissue injury'. *Biochem. J.* 222, 1-15.
4. Vani T, Rajini M, Sarkar S and Shishoo CJ (1997), 'Antioxidant properties of the Ayurvedic formulation-Triphala and its constituents', *Int.J.Pharmac.* 35(5), 313-317.
5. Buritis M. And Bucar F. (1999). Antioxidant activity of *Nigella sativa* essential oil. *Phytother. Res.*, 14: 323 – 328.

6. Material Safety Data Sheet on DCA (Glen Research). 3/24/2009 [http://www.glenresearch.com/MSDS/reagents/m40-4044-XX.pdf]
7. Stacpoole PW, Greene YJ. Dichloroacetate. *Diabetes Care*. 1992 Jun; 15(6):785-91. [PUBMED]
8. Stacpoole PW. The pharmacology of dichloroacetate. *Metabolism*. 1989 Nov; 38(11):1124-44. [PUBMED]
9. S. U. Ponnamma and K. Manjunath *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences* 2012.
10. Gomathi Rajashyamala L, Elango V, Identification of bioactive components and its biological activities of *Evolvulus alsinoides* linn. A GC-MS study, *International Journal of Chemical Studies* 2015.
11. Aldose reductase inhibitory effect of selected antglycemic plants School of Chemical Sciences, S.R.T.M. University, Nanded.
12. Morenike Olutunmbi Adeoye-Isijola, Olufunmiso Olusola Olajuyigbe, Segun Gbolagade Jonathan, Roger Murugas Cooposamy. Bioactive compounds in ethanol extract of *lentinus squarrosulus* mont - a nigerian medicinal macrofungus .
13. German JB, Dillard CJ. "Saturated fats: a perspective from lactation and milk composition". *Lipids*. 2010.
14. Kromhout, Daan; et al. (1995). "Dietary Saturated and transFatty Acids and Cholesterol and 25-Year Mortality from Coronary Heart Disease: The Seven Countries Study". *Preventive Medicine*. 24 (3): 308–315. doi:10.1006/pmed. 1995.1049. PMID 7644455.
15. "The worldwide trend of using botanical drugs and strategies for developing global drugs". *BMB Reports*. 50 (3): 111–116. doi:10.5483/BMBRep.2017.50.3.221. PMC 5422022 . PMID 27998396.
16. Tracey E. Siebert, Claudia Wood, Gordon M. Elsey and Alan P. Pollnitz. *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2008, 56 (10), pp 3745–3748. URL: http://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/jf800184t. Accessed 9/10/2012.
17. N Singh, B R pandey, P Verma, M Bhalla and M Gilca. Phyto-pharmacotherapeutics of *Cyperus rotundus* Linn (Motha): An Overview *Indian Journal of natural products and resources*.
18. Njagi JM, Piero MN , Ngeranwa JJN , Njagi ENM , Kibiti CM , Njue WM , Maina D , Gathumbi PK . Assessment of Antidiabetic Potential of *Ficus Sycomorus* on Alloxan-induced Diabetic Mice , *International Journal of Diabetes Research* 2012, 1(4): 47-51
19. Jana Hajslova, Tomas ajka *Food Toxicants Analysis – Y. Picó (Editor)* 419 © 2007 Elsevier .
20. *Nature reviews , drug discovery* volume 2 , 2003.
21. Akbar Ali , Mohamed El Badawy , Raza Shah , Wajid Rehman , Yeldez El kilany , El Sayed H El Ashry1, and Nawaz Tahir . Synthesis, Characterization and In-Silico ADMET Screening of Mono- and Dicarbomethoxylated 6,6'-Methylenebis(2-cyclohexyl-4-methylphenol) and Their Hydrazides and Hydrazones . *Pelagia Research Library Der Chemica Sinica*, 2017, 8(4):446-460
22. Elizabeth thomas, Aneesh T. P, Della grace thomas, R. Anandan. GC-MS anal phytochemicals Compounds present in Rhizomes *Nervilia aragoana gaud* , *Asian journal of pharmaceuticals and clinical research* , Vol 6, Suppl 3, 2013.
23. Odey M.O, Iwara I.A, Udiba U.U, Johnson J.T, Inekwe, U.V, Asenye M.E., Victor O , Preparation of Plant Extracts from Indigenous Medicinal Plants, *International Journal of Science and Technology* Volume 1 No. 12, December, 2012.
24. N Hema, A Ramakrishna, KN Sunil kumar , N Anupama . Evaluation of Phytochemical standards of *Cyperus rotundus* rizome with Phytochemical and HPLC profiling of its extracts, *International research journal of pharmacy* 2013.
25. www.diabetes.org.uk

54878478451180619

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

ALL SUBMISSIONS SCREENED BY

crossref
Member

JOURNAL
INDEX

Akademik Dizin
Akademi Tak Sengaja Riset